

Article

Conscious Discipline Program Towards Development of Social Foundation Skills in the Context of Early Childhood Education

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Abstract:

Conscious discipline is a social-emotional learning program for parents, educators, and mental health professionals emphasizing behavior modeling and problem-solving rather than punishment for misbehavior. Given the importance of conscious discipline (CD), this research assessed teachers' attitudes towards the CD program and the extent of integration in early childhood classrooms in developing students' social foundation skills. In this study, the inquiry approach described the variables and relationships between and among them. The descriptive correlational design provided researchers across research disciplines with a rigorous approach to answering research questions. Based on the findings, implementation of conscious discipline program helps develop the social foundation skills in early childhood education. However, it was perceived that Transition times in the classroom, students' ability to self-regulate, lack of parental support, and lack of teachers' professional development training are the teachers' significant challenges in helping their students develop social foundation skills.

Keywords: Conscious Discipline, Social Foundation Skills, Early Childhood Education

Introduction

Classroom behavior management is a critical aspect of teaching and learning, as it helps to create a positive learning environment and ensures that students are engaged and motivated to learn (Franklin & Harrington, 2019; Frey, 2019). Previous research showed that conscious discipline is a comprehensive approach to behavior management that emphasizes the importance of social-emotional learning and positive relationships in the classroom (Anderson et al., 2020). Darling et al (2020) emphasized that conscious discipline builds positive relationships with students as a foundation for behavior management. Moreover, Murphy (2020) suggests that conscious discipline is an approach to behavior management that emphasizes the importance of

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social-emotional learning, positive relationships, and a safe and supportive environment.

According to Anderson, Wimer & Fuhs (2020) conscious discipline is an important approach to education because it emphasizes the importance of social-emotional learning, positive relationships, and a safe and supportive environment. For instance, conscious discipline helps create a positive and productive learning environment that supports student success (Specht (2020), emphasizes the importance of emotional well-being in education (Caldarella et al. (2012), building positive relationships with students as a foundation for education (Cooper, 2019), provides a comprehensive approach to behavior management that focuses on prevention rather than punishment (Chavez, 2014), and creation of a positive school culture that values respect, kindness, and cooperation (Finn, 2015). Moreover, according to Drake (2020) conscious discipline is an important approach to education because it supports student success, promotes emotional well-being, builds positive relationships, prevents behavior problems, and supports a positive school culture.

While it has many benefits, there are also some potential issues that may arise when implementing conscious discipline in the classroom. For example, implementing Conscious Discipline in the classroom requires a significant amount of time and resources (Wilburn et al., 2020). It requires training for teachers, staff, and parents, and ongoing support to maintain consistency in the approach (Mahoney et al., 2021). Teachers need to create a structured environment that supports the approach, which can be time-consuming and some teachers and students may resist change, and the implementation of conscious discipline may be met with skepticism or reluctance (Farr et al., 2020). It can take time to shift the mindset and culture of the classroom to align with the approach and assumes that all children have the same needs and responds to the same strategies (Gonzales et al., 2019). Teachers need to be able to adapt the approach to meet the needs of each individual student in conscious discipline and requires a deep understanding of child development, neuroscience, and psychology (Anderson et al., 2022). Teachers who do not have a strong foundation in these areas may struggle to implement the approach effectively (Cruz et al., 2021). While, conscious discipline has many benefits, it is essential to be aware of the potential issues that may arise when implementing this approach in the classroom. By addressing these issues and providing ongoing support, teachers can create a safe,

connected, and respectful learning environment that supports the growth and development of all students.

As society's norms and expectations of student behavior have changed, behavior management has become more critical. Prince George's County Public Schools in Maryland, U.S.A., has always supported their teachers, administrators, and staff in ensuring that an effective behavior management program is set in the classroom to support student success. PGCPS has put in place Conscious Discipline program in the early childhood department beginning in 2015 as a strong foundation of social-emotional skills to manage classroom behavior and discipline among children from prekindergarten to third grade. As educators and students aim for meaningful relationships, this program is being utilized for training them to interact in ways that promote mutual respect and responsive attunement.

As an early childhood teacher and one of the participants and recipients of the Maryland Model for School Readiness (MMSR), the researcher examined the significant development it provides among early learners in the classroom. MMSR is a statewide system that supports school readiness, including instruction, assessment, professional development opportunities, transition practices, family communication, collaboration, and coordination between early childhood teachers. It is empowered by the Conscious Discipline program to promote social-emotional development. Utilizing the theory allows the researcher to distinguish the possibilities and opportunities it offers. The researcher can see the importance of the positive attitude of teachers and the full utilization of Conscious Discipline in the classroom to establish the significance and advantages of the program. Along this premise, this study intends to look into the extent of the early childhood educator's attitude and utilization of the Conscious Discipline program in Prince George's County Public Schools, findings of which would be a basis for the formulation of an action plan.

Conscious Discipline

Conscious Discipline was developed by Dr. Becky Bailey (2000) and it's grounded in the fields of child psychology, neuroscience, and ethical upbringing. (Bailey, 2017). According to Bailey (2000) conscious discipline is an interdisciplinary approach to classroom management that integrates children's social, emotional, physical, cultural, and cognitive development for optimal growth. Moreover, Nelson (2021) emphasized that conscious discipline uses the activities and classroom routines to teach the children problem solving skills in addition to providing the children with a sense of safety. Conscious Discipline is based on the premise that individuals can only change if they want to,

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that relationships are the basis for behavior management, and that conflict is required for learning, teaching, and building connections to occur (Caldarella et al., 2012). At its core, Conscious Discipline is about the personal growth of the adult, and the personal growth of the child while raising the emotional intelligence of the adults present in the child's world. While more research needs to be conducted on the conscious discipline, the existing research indicated that the conscious discipline does influence a reduction in the display of challenging behaviors in early childhood education classrooms (Nelson, 2021).

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Age Profile of the Teachers' Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
61 and above	5	14.29
51 to 60	8	22.86
46 to 50	9	25.71
41 to 45	7	20.00
36 to 40	5	14.29
26 to 30	1	2.86
Total	35	100.00

Table 1 showed that most respondents belonged to the age level of 46 to 50 with a frequency of 9 or 25.71 percent in the distribution. With another closer look at the table, the respondents are almost equally distributed in the age ranges from 36 to 40 years and above. Only one, or 2.86 percent, is within the 26 – 30 age range. It indicates that most teachers had adequately developed their teaching careers.

Table 2. Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	34	97.14
Male	1	2.86
Total	35	100.00

Regarding gender, the dominant group is female, with a frequency of 34 or 97.14 percent, and the male respondents have a frequency of 1 or 2.86 percent. The findings are accurate to the researcher's observation of the dominant population of female teachers in most educational institutions. It also implies that females predominate in the country's teaching profession in early childhood education.

Table 3. Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	23	65.71
Divorced	6	17.14
Single	4	11.43
Widow/ Widower	2	5.71
Total	35	100.00

The marital status profile of the teachers' respondents is shown in Table 3. Most of the respondents are married, with a frequency of 23 or 65.71 percent. The findings reveal that most of the teacher respondents were married. This finding is corroborated by the age of the respondents, who have already reached the age bracket of adulthood from 26 years and above, thus having their own families to take care of while doing their responsibilities in line with their teaching career.

Table 4. Ethnicity or Race

Race	Frequency	Percentage
Black	16	45.71
Asian	10	28.57
White	8	22.86
Hispanic	1	2.86
Total	35	100.00

The ethnicity or race profile of the teachers' respondents is shown in table 4. Most of the respondents are Black, with a frequency of 16 or 45.71 percent, followed by Asians, having a frequency of 10 or 28.57 percent. Eight or 22.86 percent in the ethnicity or race profile of the teachers' respondents are White, and the Hispanics with a frequency of 1 or 2.86 percent are completing the profile.

Table 5. Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Ph.D./ Ed. D.	5	14.29
with Ph.D./ Ed. D. credits	1	2.86
MA/MS	13	37.14
MA/MS credits	3	8.57
Baccalaureate Degree	7	20.00
with Baccalaureate credits	2	5.71
Associate's Degree	3	8.57
Highschool Diploma	1	2.86
Total	35	100.00

The highest educational attainment profile of the teacher's respondents is displayed in table 5. Most teacher respondents have MA/MS degrees,

with a frequency of 13 or 37.14. The finding indicates that teachers are particular about their professional growth and development; hence they looked for opportunities to continue further studies and acquire MS/MA degrees or Ph. D. and even took related courses to their present teaching load.

Grade Level Teaching Assignments	Frequency	Percentage
Prekindergarten	26	74.29
Kindergarten	9	25.71
Total	35	100.00

Table 6. Grade Level Teaching Assignment

The grade-level teaching assignments profile of the teacher respondents is displayed in table 6. There are 26, or 74.29 percent, in prekindergarten and nine, or 25.71 percent, in kindergarten.

Table 7. Length of Teaching Experience

Length of Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
26 years and above	5	14.29
21 to 25 years	6	17.14
16 to 20 years	14	40.00
11 to 15 years	5	14.29
6 to 10 years	1	2.86
1 to 5 years	4	11.43
Total	35	100.00

The length of teaching experience in the early childhood profile of the teachers' respondents is displayed in Table 7. Most of the teaching experience in the early childhood profile of the teachers' respondents is 16 to 20 years, with a frequency of 14 or 40 percent.

Table 8. Average Number of Students in Class

Average Number of Students in Class	Frequency	Percentage
20 and above	5	14.29
16 to 19	15	42.86
11 to 15	6	17.14
6 to 10	8	22.86
1 to 5	1	2.86
Total	35	100.00

The average number of students in the class profile of the teacher respondents is displayed in Table 8. It reveals that 15 or 42.86 percent of the total respondents had a class size of 16 to 19 students per class, and the lowest is only 1 or 2.86 percent of teacher respondents with only 1 -5 students.

Table 9. Length of Training and Seminars Attended

Length of Training and Seminars Attended	Frequency	Percentage
51 hours and above	11	31.43
41 to 50 hours	4	11.43
31 to 40 hours	9	25.71
21 to 30 hours	5	14.29
11 to 20 hours	4	11.43
1 to 10 hours	2	5.71
Total	35	100.00

The majority of the length of training and seminars attended profile of the teachers' respondents is 51 hours and above, having a frequency of 11 or 31.43 percent. Only two, or 5.71 percent, fall within the 1–10-hour bracket. As revealed in Table 9, most teacher respondents have attended numerous training and seminars on developing students' social foundation skills for the past five years. PGCPs and its early childhood department ensure that prekindergarten and kindergarten teachers are well-informed, knowledgeable, and trained to help students develop their social foundation skills.

Table 10. Training and Seminars Attended on Conscious Discipline for the Past Five Years

Length of Training and Seminars Attended	Frequency	Percentage
51 hours and above	3	8.57
41 to 50 hours	2	5.71
31 to 40 hours	3	8.57
21 to 30 hours	11	31.43
11 to 20 hours	9	25.71
1 to 10 hours	7	20.00
Total	35	100.00

As presented in Table 10, the majority of the training and seminars attended profile of the teachers' respondents is 21 to 30 hours with a frequency of 11 or 31.43 percent. A general profile in terms of seminars and training attended relevant to conscious discipline; it is clear that the majority or a total of 70.14 percent of the respondents have earned from ranges 1-10 to 21-30 hours. Table 10 shows that most teacher respondents have attended training and seminars on conscious discipline programs with less than 30 hours for the past five years. The data is still an acceptable rate considering that Conscious Discipline is a newly adopted program in the district. However, it also shows some of the teacher respondents' lack of motivation for professional development.

Table 11. Level of Teacher's Attitudes towards Conscious Discipline Program

	Statements	WM	D
1	A healthy family with consistently caring adults is the ultimate cultural model for optimal development and learning.	3.83	Very High
2	Building meaningful relationship and connection with children lead to more cooperative behavior.	3.86	Very High
3	Emotionally intelligent teachers and students are better equipped to create a positive and healthy educational climate.	3.83	Very High
4	An effective classroom creates a culture based on safety, connection, and problem-solving instead of external reward and punishment.	3.69	Very High
5	All behavior, whether positive or negative, is a form of communication.	3.71	Very High
6	Effective teaching requires the adult to model the behaviors they want children to develop.	3.83	Very High
7	Attempting to use force to make children behave strips their willpower and self-worth.	3.20	High
8	Every person is in charge of his/her own choices, behavior, and consequence	3.57	Very High
9	Children who learn to reflect on their feelings, choices, and outcomes become conscious of their own actions.	3.80	Very High
10	Conscious Discipline integrates social-emotional learning, school culture, and Discipline in the classroom.	3.71	Very High

As shown in Table 11, the level of attitudes of prekindergarten and kindergarten teachers towards the Conscious Discipline program has an average weighted mean is 3.70, which means very high. On the other hand, Statement#7, which says attempting to use force to make children behave strips their willpower and self-worth has a weighted mean of 3.20 which means high. The rest of the identified statements have a rating of very high. The findings of the said table imply that teachers have a very high level of attitude towards conscious discipline programs. Thus, they will continue integrating and utilizing it within and outside the classroom to help students develop social foundation skills. Most teachers agree that Conscious Discipline is a viable behavior management model to use in the classroom and has positively impacted students (Hill, 2017). Conscious Discipline leads teachers, providers, schools, and programs through a transformational process that promotes permanent behavior change. The change is from an unconscious, traditional compliance model of Discipline to a conscious, relationship-based, community model. It is built on three completely different areas: connectedness governs behavior, controlling and

changing ourselves is possible and has a profound impact on others, and conflict is an opportunity to teach (Bailey, 2000).

Table 12. Extent Of Teachers' Utilization of Conscious Discipline in the classroom

	Statements	WM	D
1	Teacher posts visuals and pictures of class schedules, routines, rituals, and behavior expectations in the classroom.	3.94	Well Utilized
2	The class practices "Brain Smart Start (Unite, Disengage Stress, Connect and Commit) as a part of the morning routine.	3.09	Utilized
3	Teachers and students practice breathing exercises and calming strategies to reduce and manage stress.	3.60	Well Utilized
4	Students can freely access "Safe Place" when they are angry, frustrated, sad, or scared in order to become calm and maintain control.	3.71	Well Utilized
5	The teacher offers students two positive choices (i.e., "You may clean up your toys by yourself or with a friend.") instead of giving an assertive command.	3.34	Well Utilized
6	Students use "brain breaks" like games, songs, and movements approximately every 20 minutes throughout the day.	3.71	Well Utilized
7	"Friends and Family Board (or Book)" includes photos of students' families, friends, and all the people who love, support, and keep them safe.	3.14	Utilized
8	The class uses the "Kindness Tree" or any form of recognition to honor kind and helpful acts among students and teachers.	3.11	Utilized
9	Students communicate negative and positive emotions verbally and physically.	3.40	Well Utilized
10	Teacher maintains composure and responds wisely and calmly to student misbehavior.	3.71	Well Utilized

As revealed in Table 12, the average weighted mean is 3.48, which means well utilized. It could be gleaned from the data that Statement 1 Teachers post visuals and pictures of class schedules, routines, rituals, and behavior expectations in the classroom got the highest weighted mean of 3.94 or well utilized. Such findings must have benefited teachers as one best way to help the students build their social foundation skills. In Statement 2, the class practices "Brain Smart Start (Unite, Disengage Stress, Connect and Commit as a part of the morning routine; statement 7, "Friends and Family Board (or Book)," includes photos of students' family, friends, and all the people who love, support and keep them safe; and statement 8, the class uses the "Kindness Tree" or any form of recognition to honor kind and helpful acts among

students and teachers, 3.09, 3.14, 3.11, respectively, with a rating of utilized. The rest of the identified statements have a rating of well utilized. The finding of the said table implies that all teacher respondents utilized, if not well utilized, conscious discipline program in their respective classrooms, and thus, there is a possibility that they will continue to integrate and utilize it within and outside the classroom setting in order to help students develop social foundation skills. It shows that the extent of the teachers' utilization of conscious discipline program reflects on their classroom's physical presentation; the teachers' and students' ability to recognize and manage physiological and emotional upset and conflicts; and the culture in the classroom that motivates teachers' and students' connection and healthy relationship. Conscious Discipline empowers adults to first connect with children, then coach children with the new skill(s) needed through administering natural consequences. Then, when they introduce a logical consequence, it will be effective.

Table 13. Teachers' Level of Effectiveness in the Utilization of Conscious Discipline Program in the Classroom

	Statements	WD	D
1	Conscious Discipline improves the quality of student-teacher interactions	3.74	Highly Effective
2	Conscious Discipline improves the social and emotional behavior of students	3.71	Highly Effective
3	Conscious Discipline reduces aggression in classrooms	3.49	Highly Effective
4	Conscious Discipline increases student academic readiness and achievement	3.54	Highly Effective
5	Conscious Discipline decreases impulsivity and hyperactivity in challenging children	3.34	Highly Effective
6	Conscious Discipline improves the social and emotional behavior of teachers	3.57	Highly Effective
7	Conscious Discipline improves the classroom and school climate	3.66	Highly Effective

Table 13 reveals the respondents' level of effectiveness in the utilization of the Conscious Discipline program in the classroom, with an average weighted mean is 3.58 or highly effective. All of the identified statements have a rating of highly effective. A closer look at the Table, Statement 1 got the highest mean of 3.74, or highly effective. It goes to show that the respondents agreed that Conscious Discipline improved the quality of student-teacher interaction. This finding implies that all teacher respondents find the utilization of the Conscious Discipline program to be highly effective. Thus, they will continue integrating and utilizing it within and outside the classroom to help students develop

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social foundation skills. It shows that teachers better understand that the Conscious Discipline model contrasts significantly with the traditional approach based on control rather than connection. The power in the classroom is shared in that both the teacher and the student are responsible for their behavior. It empowers that teacher as a self-disciplined adult who, in turn, teaches children how to become self-disciplined. According to Bailey (2000), Conscious Discipline requires adults to possess the skills they hope to pass on to children. Teaching requires adults to have the skills that they want to teach to the children (Bailey, 2000).

Table 14. Demographic Profile and Level of Attitude toward Conscious Discipline Program

Test of Significant Relationship Between the Level of Attitude toward Conscious Discipline Program and	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Computed χ^2 Value (Average)	Critical χ^2 Value	Decision	Remarks
Teacher Respondents' Age	15	6.41	< 25.00	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Gender	3	0.42	< 7.82	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Marital Status	9	7.97	< 16.92	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Ethnicity or Race	9	5.07	< 16.92	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment	21	12.32	< 31.41	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Grade-Level Teaching Assignments	3	0.56	< 7.82	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Years of Teaching Experience in Early Childhood	15	8.22	< 25.00	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Average Number of Students in Class	12	5.71	< 21.03	Accept H_0	Insignificant

Teacher Respondents' Training and Seminars Attended on Developing Students' Social Foundation Skills for the Past Five Years	15	9.23	<	25.00	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Training and Seminars Attended on Conscious Discipline Training for the Past Five Years	15	7.03	<	25.00	Accept H ₀	Insignificant

From the results reflected in Table 14, the computed values are lesser than the critical value. At a 0.05 significance level, the decision is to reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis. The null here is no relationship between the identified demographic profile of the respondents and their level of attitude toward the Conscious Discipline program. It means that regardless of age, gender, marital status, ethnicity or race, highest educational attainment, grade level teaching assignments, years of teaching experience in ECE, the average number of students in class, and training and seminars attended to develop social foundation skills of the students, all these do not influence the level of attitude of respondents toward conscious Discipline or the other way around.

Table 15. Demographic Profile and the Extent of Utilization toward the Conscious Discipline Program

Test of Significant Relationship Between the Level of Attitude toward Conscious Discipline Program and	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Computed χ^2 Value (Average)	Critical χ^2 Value	Decision	Remarks
Teacher Respondents' Age	15	10.51	< 25.00	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Gender	3	1.27	< 7.82	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Marital Status	9	8.33	< 16.92	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Ethnicity or Race	9	10.81	< 16.92	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment	21	20.22	< 31.41	Accept H ₀	Insignificant

Teacher Respondents' Grade-Level Teaching Assignments	3	2.14	<	7.82	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Years of Teaching Experience in Early Childhood	15	12.62	<	25.00	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Average Number of Students in Class	12	10.98	<	21.03	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Training and Seminars Attended on Developing Students' Social Foundation Skills for the Past Five Years	15	14.20	<	25.00	Accept H ₀	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Training and Seminars Attended on Conscious Discipline Training for the Past Five Years	15	11.65	<	25.00	Accept H ₀	Insignificant

The results in the table show that the computed values are lesser than the critical value. At a 0.05 significance level, the decision is to reject the alternative hypothesis. As stated by the null hypothesis, there is no relationship between the teachers' extent of utilization toward the conscious discipline program and their identified demographic profiles such as age, gender, marital status, ethnicity or race, highest educational attainment, grade level teaching assignments, years of teaching experience in early childhood, the average number of students in class, training and seminars attended on developing students social foundation skills for the past five years and training and seminars attended on conscious discipline training for the past five years. Hence, all these identified demographic profiles have no bearing on teachers' utilization of the conscious discipline program.

From the results in Table 16, the computed values are lesser than the critical value. At a 0.05 significance level, the decision is to reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis. As stated by the null hypothesis, there is no relationship between the teachers' effectiveness in the utilization of the Conscious Discipline program and their identified demographic profiles in terms of age, gender, marital status, ethnicity or race, highest educational attainment, grade level teaching assignments, years of teaching experience in early childhood, the average number of students in class, training and seminars attended on developing students social foundation skills for the past five years, and training and seminars attended on conscious discipline training for the past five years

Table 16. Test of Significant Relationship Between the Level of Attitude toward Conscious Discipline Program

Test of Significant Relationship Between the Level of Attitude toward Conscious Discipline Program	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Computed χ^2 Value (Average)	Critical χ^2 Value	Decision	Remarks
Teacher Respondents' Age	15	6.37	< 25.00	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Gender	3	0.86	< 7.82	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Marital Status	9	9.86	< 16.92	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Ethnicity or Race	9	8.72	< 16.92	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment	21	17.00	< 31.41	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Grade-Level Teaching Assignments	3	0.67	< 7.82	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Years of Teaching Experience in Early Childhood	15	10.22	< 25.00	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Average Number of Students in Class	12	5.69	< 21.03	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Training and Seminars Attended on Developing Students' Social Foundation Skills for the Past Five Years	15	9.48	< 25.00	Accept H_0	Insignificant
Teacher Respondents' Training and Seminars Attended on Conscious Discipline Training for the Past Five Years	15	6.91	< 25.00	Accept H_0	Insignificant

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Moreover, findings also revealed that in terms of challenges encountered by the teachers in helping the students develop social foundation skills, different themes evolved on the challenges the teachers met in helping the students develop social foundation skills, such as transition time, students' ability to self-regulate, lack of parental support, and lack of professional development training. In general, teacher-respondents identified these challenges affecting their ability to help students develop their social foundation skills.

Discussion

Based on the findings, on the demographic profile of the respondents, it was found that they were 26 years old and above, and in terms of gender, the dominant group was female. The majority of them were married, and most were Black. Most teacher respondents attained their MA/MS degree in educational attainment. The respondents were composed of prekindergarten teachers and kindergarten teachers. Most respondents have already earned more than 16 years of teaching experience. The average number of students per class was from 16- 19. Most respondents had an average of 51 hours and above in training, and seminars attended on developing students' social foundation skills and 21 to 30 hours in the Conscious Discipline program for the past five years. The result revealed that the respondents had a very high level of attitude towards the Conscious Discipline program. It was found that the respondents well utilized the Conscious Discipline program in their respective classrooms. On the teachers' level of effectiveness in the utilization of the Conscious Discipline program in the classroom, respondents stated that the utilization was highly effective. It was reported that the respondents' level of attitude toward the Conscious Discipline program, extent of utilization of the Conscious Discipline program, and the effectiveness in the utilization of the Conscious Discipline program has no significant relationship with the demographic profile of the respondents; hence the null hypothesis was accepted.

Conclusion

Conscious discipline recognizes the importance of addressing the social-emotional needs of students in order to support academic success. By creating a safe and supportive learning environment, students are better able to focus on their academic goals and achieve success in the classroom. Based on the study's findings, integrating the Conscious Discipline program in prekindergarten and kindergarten

classrooms in Prince George's County Public Schools in Maryland, U.S.A., helps to develop social foundation skills in Early Childhood Education. Moreover, transition times in the classroom, students' ability to self-regulate, lack of parental support, and lack of teachers' professional development training are the teachers' significant challenges in helping their students develop social foundation skills. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that prekindergarten and kindergarten teachers of Prince George's County Public Schools continue to utilize and integrate the conscious discipline program in and outside the classrooms with fidelity. Its significant contributions in improving the social foundation skills of early childhood students can be extended across grade levels in elementary, middle, and high school. Stakeholders should consider expanding the conscious discipline program's implementation in PGCPS.

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